

DISTENDER D8.2 DSS Architecture

D8.2: DSS Architecture
WP 8, T 8.2

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1. Introduction

This document is a formal deliverable of the DISTENDER project and was developed within Work Package 8: Decision Support System, Task 8.2: DSS Design.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to describe the design (architecture, features and technology constraints) of the DISTENDER Decision Support System (DSS) aimed to support decision-makers in planning the activity of adaptation and mitigation strategies in response to climate change. The design described here will be taken into consideration during the development phase of the DSS prototype in Task 8.3. The included assumptions are valid and applicable for the prototype only. The design of the final version will be a subject to discuss.

1.2 Scope

This document provides a description of the technological and methodological aspects of the DSS development process. It is based on “D8.1 User Requirements”, which began to answer the question “what system is going to be implemented”, defining groups of its users, the cases of using it, and fundamental user requirements, both functional and non-functional. “D8.2 DSS Architecture” answers the question “how the DSS will be implemented”. The information contained in this document should be a basis for the DSS implementation at least at the prototype stage (fed with real or dummy data sets). As we say DSS in the document we refer to the prototype DSS that will be delivered as Deliverable 8.3..

There are a number of standards and conventions that ITTI will be following (e.g. IEEE 1016-2009, IDEF4). This document does not describe all detailed software engineering standards and conventions used within ITTI.

1.3 Overview

The general structure of the document is as follows:

- **Section 1 Introduction** – (this section) describes the purpose and gives a summary of the document,

- **Section 2 Terms, Definitions and Abbreviated Terms** – provides a list of acronyms and terms used throughout this document,
- **Section 3 DSS Overview** – provides a high-level overview of the Decision Support System,
- **Section 4 DSS Architecture** – presents a path from functionality to development aspects,
- **Section 5 DSS Data Design** – describes data model elements and crucial data operations,
- **Section 6 Component Design** – provides a set of components and relations among them, as well as deployment environment,
- **Section 7 GUI Design** – presents examples of GUI layout design,
- **Section 8 Conclusions** – summarises the whole document.

It is worth emphasizing that understanding the scope of information presented in the document requires a certain level of IT background. Sections 3, 4 and 5 are described in technical terms. The assumptions contained therein are presented in a more understandable manner in section 7.

In addition to the above-mentioned sections the document contains a list of reference documents and Appendix A mapping of the identified functions to the user requirements documented in D8.1.

2. Terms, Definitions, and Abbreviated Terms

This part defines the technical terms used in this document.

2.1 Terms

Table 1 List of terms

Term	Explanation/definition
Core Case Studies (CCS)	Five case studies developed within the project representing specific areas (i.e.: Austria, the North-East of the Netherlands -, Dehesas and Montados, Guimarães and the Metropolitan City of Turin), describing the strategy taken for adaptation to climate change. In the document the CCS may be referenced also as “simulated areas”. The case studies show how robust decisions can be made based on the knowledge and information provided by the models used in DISTENDER.
Decision Support System (DSS)	In this document a software system which performs a function of advising which alternative set of initiatives are the most efficient ones to achieve a certain goal. It is a tool that supports decision makers in the development of adaptation and mitigation strategies, integrating DISTENDER results.
DSS Application	The combination of DSS subset of software components that users interact with. Different components within the application may perform the specific functions directly for an end user.
Indicator	A specific, observable and measurable characteristic/parameter used to show state, changes, or progress in a certain area
Mitigation and adaptation measure	A measure/action which aims to mitigate or adapt to the climate change consequences
Process	In Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN): a sequence of actions leading from a defined triggering event to one or more possible final states.
Strategy	A combination of actions/measures/interventions taken to address case study goals for adaptation and mitigation to climate change. Strategy and pathway are used as synonyms.

Scenario	Scenarios are plausible descriptions of how the future may develop, based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions about key relationships and driving forces. In DISTENDER the modelling includes linked climatic and socio-economic scenarios that illustrate a range of possible future worlds. From DSS perspective, scenarios are materialised in the form of indicator values changing in time.
Use case	A presentation of a possible usage of the system in the form of a sequence of simple steps
User	A person who uses or operates the system

2.2 Acronyms

Table 2 List of acronyms

Acronyms	Description
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use
ADI	Area Description Indicators
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CC	Climate Change
CCS	Core Case Studies
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
DSS	Decision Support System
EAI	Effectiveness Assessment Indicators
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IT	Information Technology
M&A	Mitigation and Adaptation
MCA	Multi-Criteria Analysis
SIM	Simulations Processing Unit (explained below)
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
SQL	Structured Query Language

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UML	Unified Modeling Language
WP	Work Package

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3. DSS Overview

An important issue in developing the Decision Support System (DSS) architecture is to understand the environment of the entire project and determine the place for the DSS in it. Taking into account the work plan of the project and the above mentioned interdependencies, the DISTENDER project environment can be divided into two processing units: the simulations processing unit (SIM) and DSS. The SIM represents the processing activities performed in WP 2 - WP7. In very general terms, information coming from global data SSP and CCS as well as simulation parameters are the input for the SIM part. The result of SIM (SIM_OUT) is used as an input for DSS, as well as, will be used in other project deliverables¹. A DSS user provides his information to the system by participating in the parameterization process, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Context of DSS in the DISTENDER project environment

The DSS outcomes (DSS_OUT) will support decision-makers in planning the activity of adaptation and mitigation strategies in response to climate change. It will be a medium to

¹ DISTENDER does not plan to dynamically integrate the different models in the DSS, but rather their outputs for the DISTENDER Case Studies. This will have a direct impact on the transferability of the project to other areas. Downscaling and impact models have high computational requirements. There is also a need to provide input data for the required study. For these reasons, both models and impacts cannot be included in the DSS but their results will be used for the development of integrated adaptation and mitigation strategies for the DISTENDER Case Studies (CS). Both the strategies themselves and the changes of the different indicators (model results) when applying the strategies are transferable to other case studies. DISTENDER has selected case studies covering a wide range of sectors and scales from national to urban so that future potential case studies can use DISTENDER results and methodology.

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present the methodological approach worked out in DISTENDER. This will include the implementations of climate only scenarios, scenarios with climate change and socio-economic change (through the SSPs) and scenarios in which adaptation and mitigation strategies are also explored. The DSS will include outputs from the full range of DISTENDER models (Water, Air Quality, Urban Heat, Health, Energy, Land Use, Agriculture and Forestry) and allow for the identification of impacts, risk and vulnerability, both before and after the application of the strategy across a range of climatic and socio-economic scenarios². Thus the outputs of WP 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 will all produce results that will act as the data underlying the DSS. These dependencies between the main information domains in DISTENDER project are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Conceptual model of the domains and their interdependencies

² Any spatial and temporal inconsistencies in different model outputs should be considered before the data is provided to WP8. It is assumed that the initial DSS data will be provided in the non-redundant structures and therefore cannot be inconsistent. As for the data multidimensionality, it is possible that in certain dimensions, the acquired data is discontinuous or contains uninterpretable values. In this case, DSS may not be able to display them. In most cases they will therefore be presented as delivered, and errors in the input data will be visible in the DSS. To avoid this or to reduce the amount of uninterpretable data to a minimum, specific recommendations have been made regarding model outputs.

The users of the system will come both from the internal environment of the project and from the outside. They will be the bodies interested in evaluating, developing, or integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies in the areas of the economy affected by climate change.

As was pointed out in D8.1, both during the project and after it ends, the main users of the system will be the policy makers supported by the DISTENDER stakeholders who are able to work on scenarios and strategies generated in the specific Core Case Studies. After the end of the project, the DSS should provide access to the publicly available results of DISTENDER to other policy makers' representatives to use the system mainly by searching and browsing the existing data, and also creating specific case studies (areas) by new users. From the point of view of system architecture, the following user categories and their roles may be defined:

- **Registered users** – policy makers allowed to view, import and change the data (i.e. representing a core case study or a follower case study provider)
- **Unregistered users** (anonymous) – policy makers allowed only to passively view the data
- **Application administrator** – a person that provides technical support and administers and supervises the ongoing maintenance of the application
- **Data administrator** – a user dealing with database management and responsible for its correct operation.

3.1 Use Case

The architecture of the system must meet the requirements and support the work of the above-mentioned users. Taking this into account, a scheme of the decision support procedure was created, which will be implemented in the system. The procedure includes 5 steps: (1) Representative cases selection³, (2) Preselection of strategies, (3) Strategies prioritisation, (4) Results visualisation, (5) Results reporting. Step 1 consists of the selection of cases, which can be manual or supported. The result of this step is a list of selected cases. Step 2 involves filtering of M&A strategies, which results in a list of selected M&A strategies. Step 3 involves setting the effectiveness criteria preferences. As a result of this step, the user will receive a list of M&A strategies ordered by priority. Step 4 is to visualise

³ Case here has the general meaning: a particular example of a considered area exposed to the climate change impact

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the data according to the settings, priorities, and preferences defined in the previous steps. The result of this step will be charts and maps showing cases and strategies, enabling user-friendly information browsing. The last step is to generate a report of the entire procedure, including the selected cases, the preferred strategies and the visualisation. This whole procedure is presented in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3 User decision support process

The architecture of the DDS system assumes user - system interaction and defines what tasks are to be performed by the user and the system. In other words, what kind of actions will be performed automatically and what user input will be required to achieve the goal. After launching, in the first step, the system will ask the user about the most representative simulation case, after which user input will be required specifying manual or supported way of making the selection. Depending on the answer, the further procedure is different. If the user chooses manual selection of relevant cases, the system goes directly to the next step. If the user selects supported selection of cases, the system displays the list of all identified characteristics from which the user selects the most appropriate. Based on the given data, the system calculates the similarity of the simulated cases and creates a list of cases from

the DSS database sorted by similarity to the user's requirements. This step ends with selecting a simulation of the case by the user. The first part of the detailed user-system interaction model is presented in Figure 4. The sequence of activities is modelled under the condition that the user is logged in and is assigned necessary privileges. Each activity is demonstrated in a specific lane concerning the DSS (light blue lane) and its user (light green lane). The sequence of the activities is depicted by direction of the attached arrows. First a user chooses whether he/she wants to indicate a simulated cases representative for his/her own area by his/her own, or he/she wants to be supported by the system. In the second case the DSS will ask for description of the user's area using predefined feature tags. A user may choose the ones that relate to his region or city. Then the system checks which of the simulated cases (areas) has the similar description to the given one and counts "similarity function". According to its value, the DSS suggests the most representative database area cases. It is possible that more than one simulated area case is assigned a very similar "similarity" assessment, so in consequence more than one record may be displayed as the result. At the end of this stage a user may select from the proposed area cases manually, deciding which datasets will be taken into account in the further processing.

Figure 4 First part of the detailed process model

The next stage of the flow is shown in Figure 5. The DSS asks a user about the method of selection of the M&A strategies he/she is interested in. The user selects them manually from the unordered list of all available strategies, or switches to the supported routine. In case of supported routine, he/she is asked how important the effects (expressed as values of effectiveness assessment indicators) are to him/her. The configuration of these “importance weights” provides the DSS with the parameters to perform a multi-criteria analysis. In effect

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a score function is counted for each strategy, which may be used to sort the list of them. This ordered list of strategies is a base for selection by the user of the ones he/she wants to consider. Only the datasets related to the selected strategies will be taken into account in further processing. This ends the second stage of the flow.

Figure 5 Middle part of the detailed process model

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The last stage of the use case concerns data visualisation and reporting and is presented in Figure 6. The DSS provides to a user a browsable list of datasets concerning the selected area case and strategy. A user may choose which datasets he/she wants to access. The DSS displays on the screen available illustrative information based on the chosen dataset. To get a hardcopy of the data the user may access the reporting function which generates the report from the selected dataset.

Figure 6 Last part of the detailed process model

The browsing or reporting function ends a considered use case of the DSS.

3.2 Process Model

Figure 7 presents the user main control flow in the DSS in the form of a process model. The difference between the use case presented in Chapter 3.1 and processes described in this

chapter is that while the use case is an exemplary instance of the user's activity in interaction with DSS, processes show a flow of control showing all possible transitions from one activity to another. The general process model for the DSS is presented in Figure x. It is modelled using the process diagram complying with the BPMN notation. It starts from the red circle marked "Start" and ends with a similar circle marked "End". The diagram consists of activities, e.g. "Main menu choice", and subprocesses, e.g. "User Project Management", connected with arrows which indicate the flow of control.

Figure 7 User Main Control Flow

The process starts from the authorisation. It is assumed that DSS may be accessed by both registered and unregistered users. Unregistered users are not required to log in to the system (they do not have a user account) but they have passive access only to selected functions (they are not allowed to change the data in the database). It also means that their activity and effects of operations will not be stored in the system to be used in the future. On the other hand the registered user after logging in to the DSS will have access to the subset of functions according to the assigned role. His/her activity will be recorded to be used in future. In this process we assume the registered user case.

After logging in to the system the user goes into the main menu loop, being able to choose a desired menu option. The main options are: general data management operation, user's account and application management, and user project management, which constitute the core functions of the DSS. Choosing the "User Project Management" subprocess, the user enters the activities described in the process diagram in Figure 8.

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First, the user may choose an existing project from the list or create a new one. The projects are assigned to a specific user as the owner and are visible only from his/her account. Once the project context is established (“Open Project”), if the results for the project are already available DSS may bypass the next steps and go directly to data visualisation. If the user needs to redefine the project parameters, he/she may go to the step of area case selection. This operation may be done manually or with support from the DSS. Then DSS lets the user filter the strategies manually or in a supported mode. Then the result visualisation and report are available.

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Figure 8 User Project Management

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Finally, a user may change the calculated project or exit the application. Some of the boxes are not simple activities. They stand for subprocesses showing the routines in detail. They will be elaborated in the next stages of the DSS development tasks.

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4. DSS Architecture

System architecture refers to the high- and medium-level design and organisation of a complex system, including its components, interactions, and relationships. It provides a blueprint for building a system that meets specific requirements. System architecture is essential for ensuring that a system operates effectively, efficiently, and reliably. It involves making important decisions about the system's structure, interfaces, and behaviour, and requires an understanding of the underlying technology and business needs. In this chapter, the fundamental concepts of system architecture are explored, including the principles and practices that govern its design and implementation. A thorough understanding of system architecture is critical for building a successful, scalable, and maintainable system.

In the process of designing the architecture of the system, it is necessary to take into account what functions the software application will provide. In the DSS application these functions will be separated into two layers: the decision support layer and the data management layer (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 DSS Application Functional Composition

Both layers contain core functions, which implement the main functional requirements. The functions included in the decision support layer (Simulated Cases Selection, Strategies Prioritisation, Results Visualisation and Results Reporting) and provided from the data management layer (User Project Management and Strategy Filtering) concern actions that can be taken by the user or the system in order to provide the user with the most important information - a list of strategies ranked in terms of importance, together with a visualisation of the effects of the implemented mitigation and adaptation measures. On the other hand, the system should also offer functions supporting the user when using the system, which are located in the data management layer (Data Import & Validation, Data Management - CRUD operations, Data Export).

4.1 Data Management Layer

The Data Management Layer groups functions related to database operations. They contain the following functional elements:

- Data Import & Validation,
- Data Management - CRUD operations,
- Data Export.

Data Import lets the user feed the DSS database with source data provided in a predefined format, e.g. CSV, Excel, or XML file. Once the user indicates source file(s), the application analyses the syntax and semantics of their contents against the assumed constraints. If any error in the data files occurs, the application indicates the error itself and marks the error in the source data file (in case of Excel file). If there are no errors in the source file(s) the data is read, transformed into the common data structure based on indicators and their arrays, maps, 3D structures, etc., and stored in the DSS database. These data are available for other operations of the DSS application.

Data CRUD operations concern basic operations on the DSS database comprising: creating new, reading, updating, and deleting existing records. It relates to the indicators themselves as well as their descriptions (metadata).

Data Export functions let the user export data from the DSS database in a defined form and format.

4.2 Decision Support Layer

The Decision Support Layer provides the specific functionality of a decision support system. It contains the following functional elements:

- Simulated Cases Selection,
- Strategies Prioritisation,
- Results Visualisation,
- Results Reporting.

4.3 Functional Architecture

Figure 10 presents the general DSS functional architecture. The architectural components are grouped in the two tiers:

- Graphical User Interface – elements building up the GUI of the application,
- Application Components – elements providing various elements of the application logic, and containing the Central Database Management Server.

In the group of GUI components one can find components displaying windows concerning functions identified in the DSS functional composition diagram. There are also specified examples of elementary operations available to the user. Four components (namely: User Project Management, Simulated Cases Selection, Strategies Filtering & Prioritisation and Results Visualisation & Reporting) are inside the box related to the operations on user projects. The hierarchy of the components is connected with the DSS main menu composition. In the group of application components there are depicted software modules being parts of the DSS application or libraries used by the GUI functions. The interdependencies are marked with dotted lines between the upper and lower parts. The data flow between the software modules and the central database is represented by arrows indicating the direction of data transmission.

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Figure 10 General DSS Functional Architecture

The general architecture of the DSS shown above may not be complete. It is possible that at the stage of implementation there will be added some necessary architectural elements.

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5. DSS Data Design

This chapter contains the description of common data model elements and key data operations in the DSS.

5.1 Data Description

Some of the data stored in the decision support system will be represented by values of indicators. The indicator is a quantitative parameter describing the modelled environment. Working with indicators can proceed properly when they are properly defined in the database. In the DSS database, indicators will be characterised accordingly using a hierarchical definition. For each indicator, its domain, aspect, subject and, finally, name will be specified. The second area (“structure”) concerns structural parameters related to location and time. Moreover, each of the values must be expressed in specific units and have defined variants (related to the context of this creation). The indicator description is presented in Figure 11 using the example of the minimum electrification rate indicator.

OD - SINGLE INDICATOR

Indicator – a quantitative parameter featuring a modelled environment

Figure 11 Indicator value description

An indicator's value is a single atomic scalar value. It will be possible to build multidimensional structures comprising many indicator instances. They may have one, two, three or more dimensions. Examples of such structures are presented in Figure 12, Figure 13, and Figure 14.

Figure 12 Array of indicators

Figure 13 Matrix of indicators (e.g. a raster map)

Figure 14 Cube of indicators

The DSS database will comprise datasets containing the current and predicted future states of the simulated environment. These datasets will be composed of values of the indicators. A certain common core of these indicators called Effectiveness Assessment Indicators (EAI) will be used for evaluation of the simulated areas (EAI are not intended to carry any evaluative function). The datasets may be arranged according to the simulated area (a territory such as e.g. a city or a region) they concern, and the M&A strategies they assume. This kind of arrangement is presented in the form of a matrix in Figure 15. For instance dataset C3 concerns area C and assumes application of strategy #2.

Figure 15 Relation of the datasets to the areas and strategy variants

While the DSS is used, two crucial data-related operations will be performed:

- Identification of the simulation area which is the most representative for the user's area (if it is not the same),
- Prioritisation of M&A strategies the most promising to achieve the goals expressed by the user as his/her preferences concerning EAI.

The first operation is shown in Figure 16. Seeking the most representative simulation area, the DSS will match the Area Description Indicators (ADI) of all stored simulation areas with the user's description of his/her area. In this comparison multi-criteria analysis (MCA) methods will be used. The best match will indicate the row of datasets that should be relevant for the user.

Figure 16 Selection of the most representative area and related datasets

The second operation of prioritisation of possible M&A strategies is modelled in Figure 17. A user provides his/her preferences assigning a normalised measure of importance to each of the EAI (or to the selected ones). Based on this information the DSS determines the effectiveness score for each dataset from the row that concerns the previously selected simulation areas. The determined dataset indicates the M&A strategy it assumes. The M&A strategies are ordered by the value of this effectiveness score.

Figure 17 Prioritisation of strategies according to EAI preferences of a user

Thanks to this operation a user is provided information on the strategy with the best fit to their request.

5.2 Data ontology

In Chapter 5.1 the entities derived from the DSS functionality are identified and relations between them are determined. They define a framework for data elements in the central database. The concepts of the Strategy of M&A measures and of the Area which the datasets concern are represented by related boxes in the diagram in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Entity Relationship Diagram

The regular indicator (a data atom) has its definition in the form of box “Indicator” and instance (specific value) shown as a box “IndicatorValue”. Specific types of variables (also atomic data elements) were extracted from the indicator concept because they describe an Area. They are represented by the following boxes: AreaProperty and AreaToProperty,

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which contain the value, at the same time it constitutes a link to the area it describes. The concept of Project (i.e. a workspace for a user) is presented as a “Project” box. It incorporates lists of strategies it takes into account as well as areas most representative for the user’s quest. The user’s area description is modelled by the entity “AreaPropertyToProject” linking a project with area properties containing a weight (determining the importance of a given feature of the area for the MCA algorithm). In a similar way any specific indicator may be linked to the project it concerns to define a weight of importance for the MCA algorithm.

The scheme is modelled in the form of a UML class diagram. Entities are shown as classes. Some of them contain attributes. The relations between them are modelled as compositions.

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6. Component Design

It is assumed that the components of the DSS will refer to the specific software modules identified in the diagram of the DSS general architecture as application components being close to the functional scope of the system. They use a central database and are presented in the upper part of the diagram in Figure 19. The whole figure concerns data use interdependencies.

Figure 19 Component Diagram

The technical and supportive components (namely: Application Administration, Application Control and Multi-criteria Analysis Modules) are shown on the left side of the diagram. They use their own databases. Application Shadow Database is a component storing the information of relevant data operations activity in any of the system databases. This information may be used to restore a stable state of the database in case of a possible malfunction and/or to trace activity of specific DSS users.

The diagram is compliant with the UML standard component diagrams. This diagram may be changed once other software components are defined as necessary to be a part of the DSS.

The exemplary deployment environment is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20 Deployment Diagram

The DSS will be made as a web-based application so for accessing it a compatible web browser on the client computer will be needed. The client computer configuration is

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presented in the upper part of the diagram. There may be optional applications installed, such as: MS Excel for preparation of imported data, QGIS for more advanced geospatial data manipulation, etc. The Client Computer accesses the Application Server shown at the bottom of the diagram. For better portability four docker containers will be installed there:

- Application Docker Container,
- Database Docker Container,
- GIS Docker Container (incl. a generic WMS/WFS server),
- Chart plotting Docker Container (incl. Chart Plotting Module - off-the-shelf application).

They will be separate parts of the DSS.

Moreover, the DSS application will contain six modules dedicated to the specific parts of its functionality:

- Data Management Module,
- Project Management Module,
- Report Module,
- Application Administration Module,
- Application Control Module,
- Multi-criteria Analysis Module.

The Database Docker Container will contain PostgreSQL Database Management System (DBMS) and PostGIS DBMS.

7. GUI Design

This chapter contains some examples of GUI design specification.

7.1 Overview of User Interface

Once a user logs in to the application he or she gets access to the main menu (to options appropriate to the user's role). The main menu consists of the following options:

- **Projects**
 - List
 - Details
 - Areas
 - Strategies
 - Results
- **Areas**
- **Strategies**
- **Parameters**
- **Help**
- **Contact**
- **Language**
- **User's profile**

The next chapter contains a screen design of the exemplary windows accessed through the main option "Project". These screens contain illustrative data used as examples.

7.2 Screen Images

In the “Project” tab, the user can see the list of projects created (or shared by another user) along with their creation dates and short descriptions. The user can also create a new project, use the filter function, reset previously applied filters to display all options and go to a specific project to view its details (Figure 21).

The screenshot shows the DISTENDER Decision Support System interface. The title bar reads "DISTENDER Decision Support System - version 1.23 release 34". The navigation menu includes "Projects", "Areas", "Strategies", "Parameters", "Help", "Contact", "English", and a user profile for "John Doe". The main content area is titled "Projects" and features a "Filter" button, a "Display all" button, and a "+ Create" button. Below this is a table with the following data:

Edit	Title	Created on	Description
	GHG emission predictions	2024-02-04 15:25:03 (UTC)	first trial
	Extreme temperature in a city	2024-03-17 21:44:29 (UTC)	Analysis for Municipality Report
	Long periods of droughts	2023-10-23 20:43:31 (UTC)	my project
	Frequency and strenght of storms	2024-01-02 12:39:01 (UTC)	
	Air pollution in a metropoly	2024-09-13 08:26:37 (UTC)	for City Planning
	Air pollution in a region surrounded by mountains	2024-02-14 14:26:44 (UTC)	testing

At the bottom of the table, there is a "Cancel" button, a status message "Total 33 items found.", a pagination control showing page 1 of 4, and a dropdown menu for "Items per page" set to 7.

Figure 21 Screen design of the DSS application, window containing a list of projects

After clicking on a project, a user can delete the project, save the changes made in the “Details” tab and go to the next tabs to display further information: “Areas” (related to a specific project), “Strategies” (presented in the context of the project) and “Results” of the project (Figure 22).

DISTENDER Decision Support System - version 1.23 release 34

Projects Areas Strategies Parameters Help Contact English John Doe

Projects

DETAILS AREAS STRATEGIES RESULTS

Title
Extreme temperature in a city

Date of creation
2024-03-17 21:44:29 (UTC)

Description
Analysis for Municipality Report

Delete Save

Figure 22 Screen design of the DSS application, window containing the project details

The “Areas” window displays the names of the specific areas along with their types (national, regional, urban) and short descriptions. The system enables filtering and displaying all options again (the latter causes deletion of the filters). The user can manually select the area or decide to apply automatic selection by using the “Match” function. In the latter case, the system itself suggests the area that best suits the user's case (Figure 23).

DISTENDER Decision Support System - version 1.23 release 34

Projects Areas Strategies Parameters Help Contact English John Doe

Projects

DETAILS AREAS STRATEGIES RESULTS

Filter Display all Match

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Type	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Austria	National	Air pollution and GHG emissions
<input type="checkbox"/>	North-East of Netherlands	Regional	Droughts, flooding, storms, ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	South-West Iberian Peninsula	Regional	Extreme temperature, water scarcity
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Guimaraes	Urban	Extreme temperature, flooding, air pollution

Total 33 items found. << 1 2 ... 3 4 >> Items per page: 4

Figure 23 Screen design of the DSS application, window containing a list of areas

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After clicking "Match", a dialog box appears where the user describes his/her area by adding tags. After entering the tags, the user clicks "Match" again, which results in a list of similar areas. The user finally chooses which area he/she is interested in and confirms the choice by clicking "Apply selection" (Figure 24).

Figure 24 Screen design of the DSS application, window for automated matching areas

In the context of the selected area, the user goes to the "Strategies" tab, where a list of strategies simulated for a given area is displayed. From the list, the user can pre-select strategies according to the aspects of interest presented in the description part (Figure 25).

Figure 25 Screen design of the DSS application, window containing a list of strategies

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Another way to choose a strategy is to use the prioritise function, where the selection is made according to specific ordering values. When the user clicks “Prioritise”, a dialog box opens with the effectiveness indicators listed (Figure 26). The user defines importance for selected indicators and applies the order to the list of strategies. The user receives an ordered list of strategies according to the scores specified in the previous step.

Figure 26 Screen design of the DSS application, window for prioritising the strategies

Going to the "Results" tab, the user gets the outcomes generated only for the strategies selected earlier. The results can be presented in various forms, e.g. as maps or charts (Figure 27).

Figure 27 Screen design of the DSS application, window for result browsing and visualisation

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After clicking “Report”, the user is presented with a dialog box with detailed data on the parameters used to generate the specific result data in the given project. The user can add his/her own description or comment to the report (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Screen design of the DSS application, window for parameterizing the report

8. Summary

The DSS Architecture document is based on the DSS User Requirements deliverable and other assumptions expressed and confirmed during technical meetings in the DISTENDER project. It describes the concept of the system on the middle level of abstraction, preparing the development team for implementation of the D8.3 DSS Prototype.

The DSS prototype, letting alone the technical framework components necessary to build its functionality into the computer application, will support a single use case (meaning the instance of a user's activities chain) presented in Chapter 3 ("DSS Overview").

The most relevant components of the DSS were identified and mentioned in Chapter 4 ("DSS Architecture"). The architectural concept is consequently used in the following chapters of the document. The architectural statements were juxtaposed with the user requirements to show the natural evolution of the concept. The coverage of the requirements by functional modules is given in Appendix A ("Function - Requirements Mapping").

Since the DSS belongs to class of data-driven decision support systems, the most important aspects of the DSS are data and data management. The semantic layer of data description was presented in Chapter 5 ("DSS Data Design"). The prototype probably will not contain real data acquired from the other WPs of the project, because they may not be ready for import at the DSS prototype delivery date. Instead it will operate on fake data (artificially created) imported from files of the similar format as the real data.

Finally, the referential deployment environment composition was proposed in Chapter 6 ("Component Design"). According to it the system will be a rather monolithic web-based application with tightly coupled supporting software libraries. It may be useful to install some standalone application on the user's computer (e.g. MS Excel, QGIS, etc.). DSS will require an online connection between the client and the server, e.g. via the Internet.

Chapter 7 ("GUI Design") contains the main menu structure as well as a set of screenshots exemplifying a user's project processing. DSS user interface will follow a user-centric approach and will be designed to use state-of-the-art window control libraries.

From the design analysis documented in this deliverable there arises that the functionality designed in this document is dependent on the scope and quality of source data. For instance, if the provided data encompass only one or two cases, the supported selection based on the multi-criteria algorithms may be too trivial, making the application not useful

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for the user. It is assumed that the number of area cases will be calculated at least for each of the DISTENDER core case studies, and possibly for some followers after the project. The number of mitigation and adaptation strategies has to be greater than or equal to 5÷6. Moreover, simulated datasets should contain relevant data and cover most of the area-strategy matrix (the system will cope with some unavailable cases). The coverage should be at least 85% of possible cases. The DSS will also require some metadata, such as, for instance, a definition of the relevant area description tags and description of each case using these tags. The description provided in this document will undergo further collaborative disambiguation and elaboration during the project meetings. The idea of the DSS prototype should be qualified for the DSS prototype implementation phase starting in May 2023. Simultaneously, additional analysis is going to be conducted which will affect the scope and functionality of DSS final version.

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Reference documents

- ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017(en) Systems and software engineering — Vocabulary
- ISO/IEC TR 19759:2015(en) Software Engineering — Guide to the software engineering body of knowledge (SWEBOK)
- IDEF4 – Integrated DEFinition for Object-Oriented Design
- IDEF1X – Integration DEFinition for information modelling
- IDEF8 – Integration DEFinition for User interface modelling
- IEEE 1016-2009 – IEEE Standard for Information Technology--Systems Design--Software Design Descriptions
- D8.1 User Requirements (DISTENDER project deliverable)

Appendix A. Function – Requirements Mapping

To ensure the backtrace from the identified functions to the specific requirements enlisted in Deliverable D8.1 “User Requirements”, the mapping matrix is provided (see Table x). It also allows a reader to verify which of the requirements were taken into account in which release of the DSS application.

Functions:

- CSF – Cases Selection
- SPF – Strategies Prioritisation
- RVF – Results Visualisation
- RRF – Results Reporting
- UPMF – User Project Management
- SFF – Strategies Filtering
- DIVF – Data Import & Validation Function
- DMF – Data Management Function
- DEF – Data Export Function
- AAF – Application Management Function

Planned releases of the DSS:

- P – First Prototype Release (D8.3)
- F – Fully Functional Release – called “Final DSS” (D8.4) in Grant Agreement.

In Table X the specific marks have the following meaning:

- P - the requirement will be taken into account in the First Prototype Release
- F - the given requirement will be taken into account in the Fully Functional Release

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- P/F - the operational part will be taken into account in the First Prototype Release, but only in the Fully Functional Prototype will the scope and quality of content data cover it entirely.

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Table x. Mapping of functions to requirements

	CSF Cases Selection	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
G01	P	P	P	P		P	P/F			
G02	P	P	P	P	P	P	F			
G03							P/F	P	P	
G04					P					P
G05							P	P	P	

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
G06	P	P	P	P						
G07							F	F	F	
G08	P	P				P				
G09 ⁱ		P/F								
G10			P	P	P	P				
G11 ⁱ										

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
G12			P	P						
G13			P/F	P/F						
G14 ⁱ							P/F	P/F		
DP01 ⁱ							P/F	P/F	P/F	
DP02 ⁱ							P/F	P/F	P/F	
DP03 ⁱ							P/F	P/F	P/F	

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
DP04 ⁱ							P/F	P/F	P/F	
DP05					P					P
DP06		P								
DP07 ⁱ		P/F					P/F	P/F		
DP08 ⁱⁱ										
DP09							P/F	P/F		

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	CSF Cases Selection	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
ID01 ⁱ							P/F	P/F	P/F	
ID02	P/F									
ID03		P/F				P/F				
ID04	P	P				P				
IN01							F	F	F	
IN02	P									

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
IN03	P	P				P				
IN04					P		P		P	
IN05						P				
IN06	P	P								
OD01	P	P								
OD02			P			P				

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
OD03	P					P				
OD04		P								
OD05						P				
OD06					P	P				
OD07			P	P						
OD08				P						

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
OD09				P						
OD10			P	P						
OD11			P	P						
OD12				P					P	
OD13			P							
OD14			P/F	P/F						

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
OD15				F						
OF16			F							
OD17			P			P				
OD18	P		P	P						
OD19			F	F						
OD20				P/F						

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
OD21			P/F	P/F						
OD22			P/F	P/F						
OD23				P/F						
OD24				P	P				P	
OD25			P	P						
OD26			P	P						

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
OD27			P							
OD28			P	P					P	
OD29			P							
MCA01		P								
MCA02		P								
MCA03 ⁱⁱ										

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
MCA04 ⁱⁱ										
DEC01				P						
DEC02			P	P	P					
DEC03 ⁱⁱ										
DEC04 ⁱⁱ										
DEC05 ⁱⁱ										

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
O1					P					
O2 ⁱⁱ										
O3 ⁱⁱ					P					
O4					P			P		
O5					P					P
O6					P					

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
O7					P					
O8 ⁱⁱ										
O9					F					
O10					F					
O11			F							
O12		F				F				

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	CSF Cases Selecti on	SPF Strategies Prioritisation	RVF Results Visualisation	RRF Results Reporting	UPMF User Project Management	SFF Strategies Filtering	DIVF Data Import & Validation Function	DMF Data Management Function	DEF Data Export Function	AAF Application Management
O13 ⁱⁱ										

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- ⁱ This requirement also concerns the scope and quality of source data to be imported into DSS.
- ⁱⁱ The requirement does not concern any functional part of the DSS.

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